

Modernization and Convergence of Youth in Chetan Bhagat's *Five Point Someone*

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Abstract

This paper delves into the themes of modernization and youth convergence in Chetan Bhagat's novel, Five Point Someone. Bhagat, a prominent voice for Indian youth, vividly portrays the social and economic challenges faced by the younger generation, particularly those from middle-class backgrounds. Set against the backdrop of Delhi, the novel offers an insightful glimpse into the lives of modern students on a technical campus. It follows three mechanical engineering students—Hari, Ryan, and Alok—whose struggles with the rigorous grading system at IIT reflect broader issues such as the competitive examination system, familial pressures, and the pursuit of a stable career amidst poverty and societal expectations. Through a first-person narrative that indirectly mirrors Bhagat's own experiences, the novel critiques the education system and highlights the immense pressure on students to achieve high grades and secure good jobs. The study explores the social behavior of Indian youth in the face of modernization, analyzing how these dynamics shape their aspirations, challenges, and resilience. By examining Bhagat's portrayal of contemporary student life and the impact of modernization, this paper aims to provide a nuanced understanding of the convergence of youth experiences in India. It underscores how Five Point Someone resonates with young Indians seeking education and employment opportunities in a globalized world, ultimately advocating for a more supportive and equitable educational environment.

Keywords: Younger generation, economic challenges, grading system, modernization

Introduction

Chetan Bhagat's *Five Point Someone: What Not to Do at IIT* serves as a seminal work in contemporary Indian literature, providing a profound commentary on the social and economic challenges faced by the younger generation, particularly those from middle-class backgrounds. Recognized as a voice of India's youth, Bhagat's novels resonate deeply with the aspirations, struggles, and realities of modern Indian society. This paper explores the themes of

Received: 12 July 2024

Revised: 26 July 2024

Accepted: 5 August 2024

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DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.13218806](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13218806)

modernization and the convergence of youth experiences in *Five Point Someone*, offering a critical examination of how these elements shape the lives and identities of young Indians. Set in Delhi, *Five Point Someone* is more than just a story about college life; it is a reflection of the broader societal pressures and expectations placed upon students in prestigious institutions like the Indian Institutes of Technology (IITs). The novel follows three mechanical engineering students—Hari, Ryan, and Alok—who, despite their academic success in gaining admission to IIT, struggle to cope with the institution's demanding grading system. Through their experiences, Bhagat sheds light on the intense competition, academic stress, and the consequential impact on mental health and personal relationships.

The novel's narrative, delivered from Hari's perspective, indirectly mirrors Bhagat's own experiences, lending authenticity and relatability to the characters' struggles. This first-person account delves into the intricacies of student life, from the menace of ragging and the burden of familial expectations to the quest for individuality and creativity in a rigid educational system. Bhagat's portrayal of these elements serves as a critique of the existing educational framework, which prioritizes grades over holistic development and stifles innovation and original thought. In addition to its critique of the educational system, the novel addresses broader themes such as the impact of modernization on today's youth. It also captures the dualities of living in a rapidly globalizing India, where traditional values and modern aspirations often collide. This convergence is evident in the characters' struggles to balance societal expectations with personal ambitions, highlighting the complexities of identity formation in a transitional society.

The focus of this paper is to analyze the social behavior of India's youth in the context of modernization, using *Five Point Someone* as a primary text. By examining the social and economic pressures depicted in the novel, this study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the challenges faced by young Indians. It also seeks to explore the coping mechanisms employed by the characters, offering insights into the resilience and adaptability of India's youth. Further, the paper discusses Bhagat's indirect call for educational reforms, advocating for a more inclusive and supportive environment that nurtures creativity and innovation. The novel's popularity and its reflection of contemporary issues underscore the need

for systemic changes in educational institutions to better serve the needs of students in a globalized world.

India's future lies in the hands of its vibrant and dynamic young population, who form a significant portion of the country's strength. According to Chetan Bhagat, this generation is a product of globalization and modernization. Bhagat suggests that the barriers to communication, both nationally and internationally, have been minimized due to modernization, a theme that is reflected in his works. Technological progress has led to a significant increase in the country's capital investments and has fostered a more open and interconnected global environment. Hence, progress is evident not just in the economic sphere of the nation but also in the way of life embraced by middle-class households.

Bhagat explores the social challenges experienced by young individuals in his novel *Five Point Someone* by depicting three distinct types of students who have opted for the same course in the same college. Through the narrative, the novel investigates the complications of suburban life and the impact of the Industrial Revolution on this generation of young Indians. These characters serve as a genuine representation of their generation as a whole.

Bhagat crafts his novels to capture the vibrant emotions of a civilization that ushers in breakthroughs in every facet of human existence. *Five Point Someone* features a cast of youthful characters from the average middle-class household in Indian society. To bring these characters to life, Bhagat paints a picture of modern India and its society as it has evolved in response to the changes brought about by modernity.

The novel's three primary protagonists come from Hindu middle-class households that place significant importance on their traditional culture and customs. However, these young individuals display a strong desire to enhance the international standing of their country. Their aspiration is to uphold the nation's reputation on both domestic and international fronts. Each of Bhagat's literary works delves into the experiences and challenges faced by those who are in pursuit of achievement and endeavoring to establish their own position within the middle-class social milieu.

Exploration of the Intersection of Youth and Modernization in *Five Point Someone*

Received: 12 July 2024

Revised: 26 July 2024

Accepted: 5 August 2024

Copyright ♥ authors 2024

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13218806>

Chetan Bhagat's *Five Point Someone* is set at the renowned Indian Institute of Technology (IIT) and follows the academic journey of three mechanical engineering students: Hari, Ryan Oberoi, and Alok Gupta. These friends face numerous challenges as they navigate the demanding educational environment. They struggle to adapt to the stringent grading standards of India's technical education system. Unlike Ryan, who is shy and achieves mediocre grades, Hari and Alok are notable for their intelligence and ease with modern technological concepts. Despite their efforts, all three friends struggle to score higher than a five on their assignments, underscoring their frustration with the grading system. Bhagat's debut novel critically examines the Indian educational system and the methods used to evaluate students' abilities. Ryan and Alok, despite their remarkable intelligence, are stymied by a system that fails to recognize their innovative approaches. Their extraordinary abilities are overlooked by both parents and teachers, leaving them confused and unsure of their identities. While addressing serious issues faced by today's youth, the book maintains a humorous tone. It delves into complex topics, encouraging readers to consider potential solutions to these educational challenges. The story concludes with a thought-provoking dilemma that invites readers to ponder the balance between student freedom and academic success. The innovations of the contemporary period, particularly technological advancements, captivate today's youth. As they grow up in a socially modern society, the younger generation finds it more appealing compared to previous generations. Young people across the nation face similar social and economic issues that have historically affected the middle class, highlighting the universal relevance of the novel's themes. *Five Point Someone* effectively captures the intersection of youth and modernization, offering insights into the evolving dynamics of Indian society.

Chetan Bhagat's novels tackle a broad range of topics, including criminality, brutality, sexuality, and economic hardship. In addition, he delves into the educational obstacles young people face when trying to gain admission to prestigious colleges and pursue opportunities that align with their interests and talents. Bhagat aims to provide a comprehensive portrayal of the current youth generation through his novels, captivating readers with his compelling writing. In an interview, he expressed his views on his readers, stating, "What attracts the readers about my

novels is not the high literature rather the simplicity of language in portraying the aspirations, mind set, and problems of the present generation youngsters" (The Hindu 2005).

Despite the novel's humorous tone, it frequently depicts unhappy incidents within the households of the three main characters. The novel explores the importance of interpersonal connections by examining the events that unfold in the lives of the three friends, as well as the dynamics between Ravi and Neha. Ryan, despite his high intellectual capacity and proficiency in completing college tasks, struggles to achieve grades higher than five points. His innate aptitude and originality go unrecognized by instructors and parents, leading to his frustration and dissatisfaction with the highly praised IIT grading system, which prioritizes marks over unique ideas. The uninspired teachers assign tasks and assessments that limit students' understanding of the lessons, causing the students to seek solace in Prof. Veera, an esteemed professor who supports them.

Bhagat accurately depicts today's youth, who often relinquish their objectives in favor of their parents' inclinations. A prime example in the narrative is Prof. Cherian's son's suicide. Unable to confront his father after failing the entrance exams, he opts for self-inflicted demise. Neha, his sister, is aware of the truth but conceals it from their father and eventually tells it to Ravi. Similarly, Alok attempts to end his own life due to feelings of depression stemming from his perception of being unable to manage his academic pursuits and his inability to graduate due to his subpar performance in the examination. Additionally, his family concerns occupy his thoughts. "That is all they talk to me about, problems and more problems" (FPS 124).

The novel explores the other side of the IITs, which are considered standard academic centers of national importance, based on the novel Five Point Someone: What Not to Do at IIT. Despite their prestigious reputation, these institutions often encourage brain-drain, resulting in a loss for Indian indigenous industry. Moreover, the tough entrance examination pattern has given rise to many private coaching centers, accessible mainly to students from wealthy backgrounds. These coaching centers create significant pressure on students' bodies and financial states of their families. It is unfortunate that the quality of teaching and research is declining in recent times.

According to a 2021 report by the Comptroller and Auditor General of India (CAG), newly established IITs are not meeting targets for faculty research, student recruitment,

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Accepted: 5 August 2024

Copyright ♥ authors 2024

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.13218806](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13218806)

retention, and infrastructure. The alarming number of student suicides in recent times demands changes in the functioning of IITs. Moreover, students taking private coaching classes are clearing the IIT-JEE entrance examination, while talented but poor students are unable to enter the institution. Bhagat's novel addresses these grave issues and argues for a change in the idea of a good student, who should be encouraged for innovative ideas rather than marks-based performance. Academic institutions must foster creativity and research over rote learning and grading systems.

Five Point Someone by Chetan Bhagat serves as a critical lens through which the challenges and pressures faced by today's youth, particularly within the educational system, are examined. The novel highlights the intersection of youth and modernization, revealing the complexities and harsh realities of navigating academic and social expectations. Bhagat's portrayal underscores the need for systemic change, advocating for an educational environment that nurtures creativity and innovation over mere academic performance. Through the experiences of Hari, Ryan, and Alok, Bhagat captures the essence of a generation striving for balance between personal aspirations and societal pressures, making Five Point Someone a significant work in contemporary Indian literature.

The work chosen for this study serves as a revelation for parents who compel their children to pursue paths that align with their own aspirations, rather than recognizing the importance of their child's individual goals. Bhagat employs a straightforward approach to presenting factual information, along with an informal style of representation, which effectively elicits emotional responses from readers. The tale exemplifies the detrimental impact of parental and teacher influence on children's creativity, as well as the consequential squandering of opportunities if creative skills are hindered. Ryan, Alok, and Hari exemplify contemporary Indian youth who possess genuine ambitions for a prosperous existence but find themselves burdened by the academic demands of the conventional educational framework. Hari's remarks describe their sense of self-esteem as a consequence of their frustrated lives: "Another five point something, another tattoo stamped on your worth as an individual in IIT society" (77).

In this modernized world, the novel Five Point Someone serves as a reminder of the significance of education in elevating the generation of young people from middle-class society.

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Accepted: 5 August 2024

Copyright ♥ authors 2024

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The development of modern technology cannot be overlooked because it has the potential to deliver a greater degree of eminence in the current context. As the famous author Pavan Varma asserts, “Job opportunities have multiplied after the reformation and modernization following the advent of information technology” (Varma, *The Great Indian Middle Class*). In our country, there has been a development of competitive educational methods that leverage technical resources. These strategies are closely associated with corporate entities, aiming to facilitate the placement of young urban technocrats in prestigious businesses offering lucrative salaries and numerous additional benefits. Professional domains serve as emblematic representations of a refined lifestyle prevalent among the contemporary middle-class populace, constituting the primary aspiration for the younger generation within our nation. Within the cohort of Indian students belonging to the new generation, a significant number of individuals aspiring to pursue computer technology express a preference for modernity due to its potential to enhance their contemporary lifestyles and foster their professional growth. Individuals have a preference for acquiring diverse social capital in both professional and personal domains. In the pursuit of professional and economic advancement, individuals must apply a diverse range of tailored techniques. These tactics encompass acquiring effective communication skills, proficiency in computer languages, participating in coaching sessions, and other related endeavors. The process of modernization in the country can facilitate the development of young individuals to a certain extent, enabling them to acquire the necessary skills and knowledge to meet the demands of corporate entities.

The central motif of the entire work revolves around the diverse concerns associated with India's educational framework. A major problem that today's youth confront is addressed in the commencement address given by Professor Cherian, the Department Head. This further evokes strong emotions in the readers as he recounts his personal life experiences. He acknowledges his errors in underestimating the academic performance of Hari, Alok, and Ryan, resulting in their poor grade points. Neha, his daughter, conceals the truth regarding her brother's demise from him, subsequently divulging it to Hari. Upon realizing his errors, Professor Cherian exhibits remorse: “When I realized that GPAs make a good student, but not a good person ... these boys have something really promising” (261). The present study, focusing on the novel *Five Point*

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Revised: 26 July 2024

Accepted: 5 August 2024

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Someone, excellently captures the academic environment of students on engineering campuses and reveals the influence of modernity on young individuals in the realms of education and professional pursuits. Bhagat strives to depict the ambitions of the younger generation from many perspectives and emphasizes the societal obstacles they face in their lives. To advance toward global modernism, the story helps readers rise above the limitations imposed by present-day cultural standards. If modernization is perceived positively, it has the potential to enhance both employment prospects and overall quality of life. Bhagat articulates his perspectives on the significant subject of the limitless influence of modernization on the contemporary generation. Being an IITian, Bhagat portrays the challenges faced by engineering graduates influenced by IIT in the novel *Five Point Someone* with a genuine autobiographical approach. The novel effectively captures the essence of the 21st-century youth, with its characters serving as representatives of contemporary Indian youth.

Conclusion

In his debut novel, *Five Point Someone*, Chetan Bhagat employs a straightforward and casual writing style to highlight the challenges faced by Indian youngsters during the current era of modernization. Each character in the narrative serves a specific purpose and conveys a clear message to the young generation of modern India. The suppression of youth in society can be attributed to various factors, including an incorrect grading system and erroneous familial ties. India places significant emphasis on the preservation of traditional cultural values, imposing certain constraints on modernization. Chetan Bhagat meticulously studies the lives of young individuals and comprehends their psychological state. Modernization has been found to have a favorable influence on the social lives of young individuals, enhancing their social standing.

References

1. Chetan, Bhagat. *Five Point Someone*, New Delhi: Rupa & Co. ,2004. Print.
2. The Hindu 11 September 2005.
3. Abrahms, M.H. *Glossary of Literary Terms*, New Delhi: Nutech Photo lithographers, 2007.
4. Iyengar, R. Srinivasan. *Indian Writing in English*, New Delhi: Sterling Publisher Private Limited, 1985. Print.

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DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.13218806](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13218806)

5. Munnum Das Biswas, Depiction of Youth Culture in Chetan Bhagat's Five Point Someone, The Criterion: An International Journal in English, Vol. IV, Issue II, April 2013.
6. Pramod, Nayar. An Introduction to Cultural Studies, New Delhi: Viva Books, 2008.
7. Tukaram, Jadhav Arvind. Representing Metropolitan Youth Culture: An assessment of Chetan Bhagat's Five Point Someone and One Night@ Call Center, The Criterion: An International Journal in English Vol.3.2, 2012. <http://www.the-criterion.com/V3/n2/Arvind.pdf>.
8. Varma, Pavan K. The Great Indian Middle Class, New Delhi: Penguin books, 2007.
9. Interview. Listen to your Heart: Bhagat, Times of India 22 Nov. 2009. Web.
10. Interview. Chetan Bhagat wants to Script Romcoms, Times of India 6 Nov. 2009. Web.